

THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICS TEACHING
METHODOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15530415>

Abstract. *The article discusses the history and theory of the emergence and development of physics teaching methodology.*

Keywords: *physics, methodology, calculation, theory, research.*

The emergence of physics teaching methodology is directly related to the teaching of physics in various schools, and it can be said that it has been in use in our Republic for a century. Its rapid development occurred in the second half of the 20th century. Therefore, it can be called a relatively young scientific direction. It is usually said that the science of teaching is covered by the science of methodology, which is derived from the Greek word *methodos*, which means “a set of methods for performing a task in a purposeful manner.” Initially, it was improved in the process of solving problems that arose in schools due to the development of society. Its development was reflected in textbooks that emerged on the basis of generalizing advanced methodological ideas. School physics textbooks created in Russia in the 18th century can be called the first manuals on the methodology of teaching it, since they selected educational material and provided some methodological instructions for teachers. Such works were founded by M.V. Lomonosov, and were further developed in the textbooks of E.Kh. Lens, K.D. Kraevich and others, created in the 19th century.

The scientifically based system of physics teaching was established in the former Soviet Union. It was determined by the methodological work of a team of scientists and teachers aimed at developing public education. In 1918, special departments of physics teaching methods were established at the Moscow and Petrograd pedagogical institutes, and later two scientific schools emerged around them. Since 1933, for almost half a century, students in the former Soviet republics have been using a physics textbook written by A.V. Pyoryshkin (sometimes with co-authors). A new period of development of physics teaching methods is directly related to the opening of pedagogical research institutes and higher pedagogical universities in the republics. Scientific research was carried out in them on modern problems of physics teaching methods.

The content and structure of the physics course, issues of polytechnic education, techniques and methods of school physics experiments, and the formation of physical concepts in students were further improved and developed. In order to increase the effectiveness of the physics teaching process, teaching methods and techniques were improved, and the use of technical means (cinema, television, etc.) was widely introduced. The content of the physics course was systematically improved based on scientific and technical achievements. In this direction, the reform of the school physics course, which was carried out in 1967-1972, was

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effective, since the scientific level of physics education was enriched with the latest achievements of physics. This work was carried out in the following areas: - interpretation of educational material from the point of view of modern physics; - introduction of some fundamental experiments and scientific foundations of modern physics into the school physics course. These circumstances were reflected in all physics textbooks. The issue of further development of physical education in secondary and higher schools due to the development of society is an objective and legitimate process. It is determined by the scientific and technological revolution and the achievements of pedagogical science.

In particular, the content of physics education is determined by its modernity and the extent to which it reflects the achievements of physics. An example of this is the partial introduction of such "great ideas" as probability, particle transformation, and corpuscular-wave dualism, and the fact that scientific research is still being conducted on these issues. In order to further develop the theory of improving physics teaching methods and develop appropriate teaching technologies, and ultimately further increase the effectiveness of the educational process, the following should be done: - identify the psychological and didactic foundations of the formation of physical concepts at different stages of teaching and develop methodological recommendations related to them, taking into account the activities of professors and students in this process;

- establish the experimental foundations of physics teaching: fundamental demonstration experiments, frontal laboratory work, experiments and observations, practicums, conducting research classes for those interested in physics, and widely using modern technical means of teaching; - it is necessary to solve such urgent methodological problems as the introduction of effective methods of assessing and systematizing students' knowledge and generalizing their knowledge, skills and abilities; - the formation of students' skills and abilities for independent learning. Based on the basic law of didactics - the law of unity of learning and teaching, the educational process should be considered from the point of view of the mutual unity of the teacher and students. Because, in order to introduce innovations in any subject into the educational process, they must first be reworked from a didactic point of view, and then they will become educational material. Of course, such processing is carried out on the basis of didactic principles, which we will get acquainted with in the next paragraph. In addition, the future physics teacher should also be well versed in the basics of psychology, because in order for students to fully master the educational material, it must correspond to their mental state. For example, if the learning material is relevant to the learning objective, it will be better learned. Learning material without a goal will not be effective.

Therefore, experienced lecturers pay special attention to fully conveying the purpose and plan of the lecture to students. Then, using questions that further increase students' interest in the subject, they try to explain the topic at a high level. If the student is not mentally ready to receive information or his views do not correspond to the content of the lecture material, the information received will not be absorbed.

Another important task of physics teaching methodology is to arm students with the methodological foundations of the educational material being taught. For this, students must be well versed in the philosophical foundations of physics and be able to interpret them. It is worth

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noting that while many famous philosophers were physicists by background, many famous physicists were also good philosophers, and many examples can be given of this. We consider it appropriate to dwell on another important issue. Until now, there are almost no works that provide information about the methodology of physics teaching, which should be in the forefront in physics teaching. It can be said that the methodology of higher education, which has been developing in recent years, has not yet been fully formed as an independent department of pedagogy. However, it can be said with confidence that the scientific and methodological conferences held at various levels, articles published in scientific and methodological journals, and dissertations defended on the improvement and development of the methodology of physics teaching in higher education serve to indicate its future place, importance, and development.

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